

MIXED-MODE INTERLAMINAR FRACTURE TESTING USING THE MMB-FIXTURE

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ABSTRACT

The interlaminar fracture behaviour of a unidirectional carbon fiber reinforced epoxy has been investigated at various mixed-mode loading conditions using the mixed-mode bending (MMB) fixture. In terms of the mixed-mode ratio G_I/G_{II} the range between 0.2 and 9.8 has been covered. To determine the critical energy release rate from the registered data the area method and a corrected beam theory have been applied.

It has been found that the critical energy release is strongly influenced by the ratio G_I/G_{II} . Moreover an increase in fracture toughness with crack length (R-curve) has been observed in some cases. Based on the values for crack initiation a failure criterion is proposed.

INTRODUCTION

Among the various types of defects that occur in fiber reinforced materials the delamination is the most critical one, since it may lead to a considerable loss of flexural stiffness and in-plane compressive strength due to the local buckling of the separated plies. If such a defect is located in a loaded angle ply laminate, crack opening will be in general of a mixed-mode type, i.e. crack opening will be a superposition of the three fundamental modes shown in figure 1. In this general case of mixed-mode crack opening it is not sufficient for the

Figure 1: The three fundamental crack opening modes.

prediction of delamination propagation to just know the interlaminar fracture toughness for pure mode I and mode II loading, which may easily be determined in standard tests (e.g. DCB respectively ELS and ENF). Moreover the delamination resistance for any mixed-mode loading is also needed.

In this study mixed-mode testing was limited to a superposition of mode I and mode II loading, which is sufficient for the analysis of the two-dimensional crack problem. However, in general mode III is also present.

Comprehensive studies concerning the mixed-mode delamination behaviour have already been done by several researchers. They used edge delamination tension (EDT) [1, 2, 3], cracked lap shear (CLS) [4] or asymmetrically loaded DCB specimens [5, 6, 7, 8]. Others achieved the mixed-mode crack opening by loading just one lever of an ELS specimen [9, 10, 11], which is shown schematically in figure 2. Here this type of test will be called mixed-mode end loaded split (MMELS). Other names are fixed ratio mixed-mode [12] and asymmetric end loaded split (AELS) [10]. Jurf and Pipes [13] as well as Yoon and Hong [14] used the Arcan test fixture for mixed-mode delamination testing.

Figure 2: Schematic sketch of a Mixed Mode End Loaded Split (MMELS) specimen.

This investigation focuses on the mixed-mode bending (MMB) test, which has been proposed by Reeder and Crews [15]. The MMB test set-up can be considered as a combination of a DCB and an ENF test. Because of geometric nonlinearities linear analysis is not appropriate for the determination of the critical energy release rate G_c and the ratio of G_I/G_{II} . According to [16] linear theory may lead to an error that could be as large as 30 %. Since the application of nonlinear theory would be rather inconvenient, the MMB apparatus was redesigned, which led to a reduced degree of nonlinearity [16, 17]. A schematic sketch of the redesigned test fixture is shown in figure 3. By varying the distance l_b and l_c the desired mixed-mode loading can be adjusted. Further details concerning the MMB test can be found in [16, 17].

Figure 3: Schematic sketch of the redesigned MMB test fixture.

The goal of this investigation has been the evaluation of the interlaminar fracture toughness for various mixed-mode (I/II) loadings using the redesigned MMB fixture. For comparison results from MMELS tests will also be presented.

EXPERIMENTAL

MATERIAL AND SPECIMEN FABRICATION

The material tested in this study is called RIGIDITE 5208/G30-500, a first generation epoxy reinforced with HT-fibers from CELION. The specimens have been cut from panels, which were cured in an autoclave according to the supplier's recommendation. The lay-up consisted of 24 unidirectional plies. The artificial precrack has been achieved by inserting a single $12 \mu\text{m}$ thick TEFLON-foil between the 12th and 13th ply.

The specimens had a length of about 250 mm, a width of $b = 25 \text{ mm}$, and a thickness of $2h \approx 3 \text{ mm}$. Their sides were coated with white typewriter correction fluid (Tipp-Ex) to enhance the visibility of the crack tip. The loading was applied by aluminum end blocks, which were bonded at the cracked end of each specimen. Figure 4 shows the specimen with its dimensions.

Figure 4: Specimen with dimensions.

TEST SET-UP

For all MMB tests the redesigned fixture shown in figure 3 has been used. The distance l_b was always equal to l and the load-point height above the specimen midplane has been chosen to be 15 mm.

By varying l and l_c the following mixed-mode ratios could be achieved.

l	l_c	G_I/G_{II}
in mm	in mm	
110	58	0.2
110	66	0.3
110	80	0.6
110	182	3.1
110	368	6.2
50	448	9.8

TEST PROCEDURE

Since the weight of the loading lever could not be neglected in comparison to the critical load for delamination propagation, it was added to the force applied by the testing machine.

The starter crack produced by the $12 \mu\text{m}$ thick TEFLON-foil was assumed to be sharp enough to measure initiation values of the interlaminar fracture toughness $G_{c,ini}$. For this reason no

precracking has been done. However, in the case of low mixed-mode ratios, i.e. when mode II was dominant, the delamination propagated in an unstable manner from its initial position to the mid-span position of the specimen, where the lever fulcrum was located. To avoid this the initial crack length had to be extended, which led to the disadvantage that for $G_I/G_{II} = 0.2, 0.3,$ and $0.6 G_{c,ini}$ could not be measured.

After the specimens had been mounted into the fixture, they were loaded until the crack length was increased by a certain increment. Then the crack tip was marked on each side of the specimen followed by an unloading. This procedure was repeated several times until the delamination front had reached the mid-span position. The load-displacement response was recorded during each fracture toughness test.

DATA REDUCTION

To determine the critical energy release rate G_c from the registered data, the area method [18, 19] and the corrected beam theory [20] have been applied.

The area method is based on the determination of the area ΔU enclosed within the loading and unloading P - δ -curves. The critical energy release rate is

$$G_{c,a} = \frac{\Delta U}{b\Delta a} \quad (1)$$

and can be understood as an average value for the corresponding crack increment.

According to the corrected beam theory [20] the energy release rate for mode I and mode II can be determined using the following equations.

$$G_I = \frac{3P^2(a + \chi_I h)^2}{b^2 E_{1b} h^3} \left[\left(1 - \frac{l_c + l_b}{2l} \right) f_2 - \frac{l_c}{l_b} f_1 \right]^2 \quad (2)$$

$$G_{II} = \frac{9P^2(a + \chi_{II} h)^2}{4b^2 E_{1b} h^3} \left[\left(1 - \frac{l_c + l_b}{2l} \right) f_2 + \frac{l_c}{l_b} f_1 \right]^2 \quad (3)$$

The flexural modulus E_{1b} was measured in 3-point bend tests to be on average 128 GPa. Adding the terms $\chi_I h$ and $\chi_{II} h$ to the crack length is a correction for the deflection and rotation at the crack tip. According to [21] χ_I is a constant, which can be calculated from the material properties.

$$\chi_I = \sqrt{\left(\frac{E_{11}}{11G_{12}} \right) \left[3 - 2 \left(\frac{\Gamma}{1 + \Gamma} \right)^2 \right]} \quad (4)$$

$$\Gamma = 1.18 \frac{\sqrt{E_{11} E_{22}}}{G_{12}} \quad (5)$$

The following values have been used throughout this study: $E_{11} = 140$ GPa, $E_{22} = 9$ GPa, and $G_{12} = 5.9$ GPa. χ_{II} may be taken to be $0.42\chi_I$ [22]. The factors f_1 and f_2 are corrections for large deformations [20]. They were in the range between 0.97 and 1.

RESULTS

LOAD-DISPLACEMENT BEHAVIOUR

The load displacement behaviour of the MMB specimens was found to be slightly nonlinear due to geometrical effects. The degree of nonlinearity increased with mixed-mode ratio

G_I/G_{II} and with crack length. Usually another type of nonlinear behaviour precedes the maximum load. It is believed that this is caused by microscopic damage. For this reason the critical load P_c is assumed to correspond to that point of the load displacement curve, where it deviates from linearity. The differences between the critical and maximum load were always less than a few percent. A typical plot of load versus cross head displacement is shown in figure 5.

Figure 5: Load-displacement plot recorded during a MMB test ($G_I/G_{II} = 0,6$).

INTERLAMINAR FRACTURE TOUGHNESS

The values of the interlaminar fracture toughness, that have been determined by the above mentioned data reduction schemes, are plotted versus $a - a_0$, a_0 being the length of the artificial crack. Figure 6 shows the critical energy release rate for a mixed-mode ratio of 0.2 and 0.3. In both cases the fracture toughness seems to be independent of the crack

Figure 6: Critical energy release rate at a mixed-mode ratio of $G_I/G_{II} = 0.2$ and 0.3 depending on crack length $a - a_0$.

length. Based on the results of the corrected beam theory it was determined to be 0.31

for $G_I/G_{II} = 0.2$ and 0.26 for $G_I/G_{II} = 0.3$. Since the specimens had already a mode I precrack, the initiation values of the fracture toughness could not be measured. However it was assumed that they could be determined by extrapolation, i.e. they are equal to the above mentioned mean value.

As a further example the fracture toughness values for $G_I/G_{II} = 3.1$ are presented in figure 7. It can be seen that G_c increases with crack length. This so-called *R*-curve was observed for all cases except for $G_I/G_{II} = 0.2$ and 0.3 .

Figure 7: Critical energy release rate at a mixed-mode ratio of $G_I/G_{II} = 3.1$ depending on crack length $a - a_0$.

Generally it can be stated that the measured data exhibit a considerable scatter, which is typical for interlaminar fracture toughness testing. As can be seen in figure 6 and 7, both data reduction schemes give similar results.

DELAMINATION INITIATION CRITERION

The initiation values of the interlaminar fracture toughness (average values with standard deviation) measured in the MMB tests are plotted in a G_I - G_{II} -diagram, which is shown in figure 8. It should be mentioned that all data points are based on the results from the corrected beam theory. Fracture toughness values for the same material, that have been determined with DCB, ELS, and MMELS specimens, are also shown in the diagram. It can be seen that the results of the MMB and MMELS tests are in good agreement.

The failure criterion

$$\frac{G_I}{G_{Ic}} + \frac{G_{II}}{G_{IIc}} = 1, \quad (6)$$

which has been suggested by many researchers, is plotted with a dashed line. It does not describe the failure behaviour correctly, but it can be considered as a conservative estimate.

Another way of plotting the fracture toughness for different mixed-mode ratios is illustrated in figure 9. The solid curve fitted through the data is described by a fifth order polynomial. It can be considered as a failure criterion for mixed-mode loading.

Figure 8: Initiation values (average and standard deviation) of the interlaminar fracture toughness for various mixed-mode ratios.

Figure 9: Initiation values (average and standard deviation) of the total fracture toughness versus G_{II}/G_{total} .

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